

Quantum Spatial Probability and Time Intervals in the High Energy Limit Part II

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In Part I of this note we argued that the quantum bound state expectation value $\langle -1/(2m) d/dx \int dx WW (-1/2m d/dx dW/dx /W) \rangle$ in the high energy limit is equivalent to the first part of the classical action: $\int dt .5mv$. As a result, we identified WW =spatial density (bound state) with $1/v(x)$ in the high energy limit. $1/v(x)$ is used in the literature (1) as probability classical(x) when calculating Shannon's entropy classically (as a bound for high energy quantum entropy). In this note, we wish to examine further some ideas associated with this link to the classical action.

Classical Action

In classical mechanics, it seems one may deal with $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ in the calculus limits. Thus, one may write both:

$$\text{Part of Action} = \int dt .5m v(t)v(t) = \int dx 1/v(x) .5mv(x)v(x) \quad ((1))$$

For the first integral, one has equally sized dt slices, while for the second equally sliced dx pieces and a weight function $1/v(x)$ which looks somewhat like a probability at least mathematically. One may note that in the second integral $dx/v(x) = dt(x)$ i.e. time slices which are not constant as $.5mv(x)v(x)$ is evaluated at x points separated by equal dx values.

In quantum mechanics, we argue that one does not really have a $dx \rightarrow 0$ limit for a bound state even in the case of high energy because there is still oscillatory behaviour in the wavefunction (e.g. consider a particle in a box or an oscillator wavefunction). Thus quantum bound states seem to focus on dx i.e. there is no time except in $\exp(-iEn t)$ and this t is not associated with a particle moving from one x point to another, but rather with cycling of $\exp(ipx)$ terms in the wavefunction (as will be further argued).

Quantum Bound State Considerations

Quantum bound states are based on average energy conservation (which is a classical notion) for all energy levels i.e.

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } KE(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W$$

As a result, $v_{rms} = \sqrt{2m KE(x)}$ is the classical velocity $v(x)$ for all energy levels. v_{rms} , however, is a mathematical construct in quantum mechanics. Unlike the classical velocity $v(x)$, it does not follow the motion of a particle from one point to another. A particle has a wavefunction which means it cannot be located at a point, but within a region. For a bound state, one does not have a pure $\exp(ipx)$, but a distribution $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but wavy (crest-trough) patterns still exist and the particle is not localized at a point. As energy increases, the

crests/troughs become narrower and might approximate a small value of dx , but not $dx \rightarrow 0$ as an actual point. As a result, considering $v_{rms}(x) = dx / dt$ for any bound state energy does not seem to lead to meaningful ideas for dx and dt at low energies.

If the energy level, however, increases enough, the width of a crest may become very small compared with the length of the system. In such a case, dx begins to approximate dx from calculus. If the bound quantum state at very high energy is to match classical physics by the correspondence principle, then $v_{rms}(x)$ should have physical meaning. The crest or trough itself gives a measure of dx , but the envelope of the wavefunction squared provides a weight or probability at each dx (width of crest) region. This weight (which is a probability) times dx (which is a constant) should be equivalent to $dt(x)$ where $v_{rms}(x) = dx(\text{constant}) / dt(x)$. Thus classical time emerges in the quantum bound state, but only in the high energy limit. For lower energy states, there is a $v_{rms}(x)$, but the dx width of the crest is so large as to have no association with v_{rms} at a point. Consequently, $v_{rms}(x) = dx$ (width of crest) / dt yields a dt which seems to be meaningless.

Time in $\exp(-iEnt)$ seems to be associated, as a result, with cycling and not any physical evolution of the bound particle. In particular, $\exp(ipx)$ terms from $W(x)$ the wavefunction receive impulse hits from $\exp(ikx)$ from $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. A particular $\exp(ip_1 x)$ may be created through many $\exp(ikx) \exp(i(p_1 - k)x)$ impulse transfers and this leads to a cycling time.

Forward and Backward Time Motion

A consequence of classical time not emerging in a quantum bound state (i.e. time-independent quantum mechanics) is that it contains a superposition of a particle moving both forwards and backwards. For low energy states, one does not know the position of a particle within a wavelength L , so near the wall, a particle with momentum p might be within a length L of the wall or may have reflected already. The notion of a particle traveling in one direction and then reflecting from a point (i.e. a wall) seems to be based on the idea of the resolution of $dx \rightarrow 0$.

Thus, even though $dt(x) = dx(\text{constant}) / v(x)$ emerges from the high energy limit of a quantum bound state, forward and backwards motion are still entwined in the quantum picture and one does not have a true correspondence between classical and high energy bound state quantum mechanics.

Meaning of Spatial Entropy Term for a Bound State

Shannon's spatial entropy for a bound state (which is part of the total entropy, we argue, which also includes momentum entropy and a cross term of $-\int \psi^* \psi \ln(\psi^* \psi) dx$ which integrates to 0), is given by:

Spatial entropy portion = $b \int dx W \ln(W)$ ((3)) where b is a constant

W for a bound state is the probability to find the particle in a region dx which is smaller than the crest size for low energy levels. Thus, W seems to be a legitimate probability. As the energy level increases, $dx W$ becomes equivalent to the classical $dt(x)$ where $v(x) = v_{rms}(x) = dx$ (crest width) / $dt(x)$. Here dx crest size becomes very small and approximates the calculus dx .

It is not so clear in this situation that one has a probability anymore even though WW is still a weight factor of dx . It may be viewed as a probability, it seems, only if one cannot follow the particle's motion deterministically which seems to hold in the quantum bound case even in the high energy limit because both forward and backward motion are simultaneously included. As a result, it seems one must be careful in interpreting the correspondence principle for a bound quantum state even in the high energy limit.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum bound states satisfy a classical average conservation of energy equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ for every energy level n . This implies that there is a $v_{rms}(x)$ at every energy level which represents classical velocity. This math construct, however, does not seem to have much meaning in a quantum bound state because the crest-trough widths are comparable to the system size for low energy levels. Thus, it does not seem to make sense to talk of a velocity at a point x if x has a large range. As energy levels rise, the crest size shrinks to the point where it might approximate dx in the calculus limit. If a correspondence principle is to hold at this level, then $dx WW$ which is used as the weight in calculating $dx WW$ $KE(x)$ where $KE(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W$ should be equivalent to $dt(x)$ where $v_{rms}(x) = dx$ (constant)/ $dt(x)$ i.e. $dt(x) = dx/v(x)$. Thus, classical time emerges in the high energy limit in the sense that $dx WW = dx 1/v(x)$ which gives $dt(x)$, the time to traverse a constant dx . It should be noted, however, that even in this limit a quantum bound state still contains forward and backward moving pieces (i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$) and so is not a classical description of a particle moving first to the right and then to the left in a bound classical system. The time in $\exp(-i E_n t)$ (the time portion of the bound state wavefunction) seems to apply to cycling and not classical evolution or motion as discussed in the note.

References

1. Majernick V. and Richterick L. Entropic Uncertainty Relations (1999)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231009385_Entropic_uncertainty_relations